

ENVIRONMENTAL EXPOSURES IN HEALTH FACILITIES

Deliverable 2.8

Environmental exposures in health facilities

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.8

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Author(s)	DTU 1. Jørn Toftum 2. Andreas Sode Vest 3. Anders Mahdi-Waldorff CeSHHAR 1. Thabani Muronzie 2. Stanley Luchters Wits RHI 1. Craig Parker 2. Otsile Lekabe Karolinska Institutet 1. Nathalie Roos
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Investigators

The heat exposure measurements were carried out by a team of investigators from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), CeSHHAR (Zimbabwe), Wits RHI (South Africa), and Karolinska Institute (Sweden). The team combines knowledge on heat exposure measurement and analysis with practical experience and access to health facilities in Zimbabwe, South Africa, and Sweden. All measurements were approved by the local facility management.

The team consists of:

- From the Technical University of Denmark, Professor, Head of Section Indoor Environment Jørn Toftum (PhD), MSc. student Anders Mahdi-Waldorf, MSc. student Andreas Sode Vest;
- From CESHAR Mr Thabani Muronzie, a Research Officer-Mitigations in the Climate, Environment and Health Department, Professor Stanley Luchters, MD, MSc PHDC, PhD. Executive Director of CeSHHAR Zimbabwe. He also has a joint appointment with the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (LSTM), UK as a Professor of Population Health and Environment.
- From Wits RHI Mr. Craig Parker, MSc, MMPDM, Data Scientist.
- Mr. Otsile Lekabe, Carbon Monitor and Data Manager.
- From Karolinska Institute Nathalie Roos (MD PhD), Senior researcher.

Partners in the project

Partners involved in the heat exposure measurements.

1. Section for Indoor Environment, Department of Environmental and Resource Engineering, Technical University of Denmark performs research on the evaluation of indoor environmental quality (IEQ), assessment of IEQ effects on occupants and their behaviour, and sustainable and resilient heating and cooling systems.
2. Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (CeSHHAR), Zimbabwe - specialises in maternal, neonatal, and child health research, community-based intervention research, and anthropology.
3. Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa - provides expertise in climate change and health, statistics, maternal health, anthropology, and intervention co-creation.
4. Karolinska Institute (KI), Sweden, is one of the world's foremost medical universities and accounts for the largest share of all academic medical research conducted in Sweden. KI also offers the country's broadest range of education in medicine and health sciences.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
ART	Antiretroviral therapy
AT	Apparent Temperature
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CHC	Community health centre
Cwa	Humid subtropical climate (Köppen-Geiger climate classification)
Dfb	Continental climate (Köppen-Geiger climate classification)
EU	European Union
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HIV/AIDS	Human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEQ	Indoor environmental quality
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KI	Karolinska Institutet (Sweden)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LSHTM	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
LSTM	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (United Kingdom)
MRT	Mean radiant temperature
NCD	Non-communicable disease
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
RH	Relative humidity
SRI	Solar reflection Index
TB	Tuberculosis
UK	United Kingdom
WBGT	Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (a heat stress index)
Wits RHI	Research institute of the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)

Definitions

Term	Definition
Adaptive thermal comfort	Comfort theory that builds on occupants' expectations in non-climate-controlled buildings and where the comfortable indoor temperature depends on the outdoor temperature
Air humidity	The concentration of water vapor present in the air is also known as 'absolute humidity' or 'humidity ratio'. It can also be referred to as 'relative' (the ratio of the partial to the saturated water vapour pressure at the same temperature and absolute pressure)
Air temperature, t_a	The temperature of the atmosphere which represents the average kinetic energy of the molecular motion in a small region and is defined in terms of a standard or calibrated thermometer in thermal equilibrium with the air
Clothing insulation, I_{cl}	Thermal insulation provided by clothing in clo or $m^2 K W^{-1}$
CO ₂ concentration	Used to evaluate the indoor air quality in rooms occupied by people. Usually, a CO ₂ concentration higher than 1000 ppm indicates unsatisfactory air quality
CO ₂ equivalent	Used to compare emissions from various greenhouse gases to an equivalent of carbon
g-factor	Window radiation transmission property
Global Warming Potential, GWP	Describes the relative potency of a greenhouse gas. Is often seen in relation to the GWP of CO ₂ (CO ₂ equivalents)
Globe temperature, t_g	The globe temperature expresses an integrated measure of the radiant and air temperatures, and it depends on the energy balance between the convective and radiant heat exchanges of the globe
Life Cycle Assessment, LCA	The process of quantifying raw material and energy requirements
Life Cycle Costing, LCC	A methodology that provides an estimate of the total capital, operating, and maintenance costs of an Asset over its operating life
Mean radiant temperature, mrt	Used to quantify the amount of radiant heat exchanged between a person and an enclosure.
Metabolic rate, M	Total energy production in a human in unit time normalised by the total body surface area of a human in Wm^{-2}
Operative temperature, t_o	Integrates the air and mean radiant temperatures in one, simple index that is often used to assess thermal comfort in buildings
Parts Per Million, ppm	Unit used to quantify concentration
Predicted Mean Vote, PMV	Predicts the mean value of the thermal sensation of a large group of persons as a function of their physical activity (metabolic rate), clothing insulation and the four environmental parameters air temperature, mean radiant temperature, air velocity and air humidity
Relative Humidity of the air, RH	The ratio of the partial to the saturated water vapour pressure at the same temperature and absolute pressure
Solar reflection Index, SRI	Indicates a roof's ability to reject solar heat
Wet Bulb Globe Temperature, WBGT	A simple index of the environment that is considered along with metabolic rate to assess the potential for heat stress among those exposed to hot conditions

Executive summary

Indoors at workplaces, adverse thermal conditions can lead to errors, reduced work performance, and even accidents. Heat may have particularly serious consequences in healthcare with patients who may be vulnerable and therefore rely on staff to be vigilant and careful.

Currently, energy used for space cooling accounts for 20% of the global CO₂ emissions from buildings. With increasing temperatures caused by climate change, the energy used to cool buildings is projected to more than triple by 2050. It is, therefore, crucial to emphasise sustainable practices in the building sector. This includes more widespread use of solutions that can moderate indoor environments at low energy use, preferably by passive means, using renewable energy, and using sustainable materials.

This deliverable contains two sections: 1) one on the measurement of thermal exposures in the maternity wards of four healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe, South Africa, and Sweden, and 2) a section that evaluates through numerical simulations the effect on the indoor thermal conditions, energy use, and sustainability of selected building-related mitigation interventions in a maternity ward at the Mt. Darwin Hospital in Zimbabwe - under a current and a projected future climate scenario.

Measurement devices recording air temperature, globe temperature and air humidity were located in selected rooms in the healthcare facilities. Based on the measured parameters, different indices were used to assess indoor thermal comfort (Sweden) or heat exposure (Zimbabwe and South Africa). Measurements in Sweden represented autumn/winter (October-January), in Zimbabwe spring/summer (September-December), and in South Africa the summer period (December and January).

In Sweden, the recorded temperatures were mainly within the highest comfort quality categories. In contrast, in the facilities in both Zimbabwe and South Africa,

temperatures were well above the recommended limits for comfortable indoor conditions. However, the relative air humidity (RH) in Sweden was lower than 20% RH in 25% of the recordings and lower than 40% RH in around 90%. This may affect the staff's perception of dry air and cause symptoms such as dry mucous membranes in the eyes, nose, mouth, and dry skin. In contrast, in South Africa and Zimbabwe, the relative air humidity was higher than 40% RH in around 75% of the recordings. In combination with a high operative temperature, the air humidity may reduce the evaporation of sweat, which is required to sustain the body's heat balance.

In South Africa, the Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) was below the reference limit for unacclimatised persons performing work at low or moderate metabolic rates almost all the time. In contrast, the reference limit for moderate work in Zimbabwe exceeded 7% of the measurements. Reference limits reflect unacclimatised persons, as healthcare workers may not be acclimatised to heat. Even though air temperatures reached relatively high levels, the air humidity during these periods was moderate, preventing excessively high WBGTs.

A virtual model of the maternity ward at Mt Darwin District Hospital was created based on observations in the hospital case building. The model was used for a year-long simulation of the indoor environment and energy use with a weather file representing the location of the hospital with the current climate and with a projection to 2080. Different refurbishment solutions were tested alone and in combination. The solutions included reflective roof paint, ventilation grilles in exterior walls, ceiling and exterior walls insulation, new windows, shading overhangs, a split-type air conditioning unit and a central air handling unit. The feasibility of the refurbishment solutions was evaluated based on their influence on the indoor environment, energy use, global warming potential, and life cycle costing.

It was possible almost to eliminate time with temperatures above 32°C when several of the refurbishment solutions were combined. As the associated costs and environmental impacts were considerably higher with the active than with the passive solutions, photovoltaics should be implemented with active solutions.

The projection for the year 2080 showed a 15-percentage point increase in yearly hours with indoor temperatures higher than 32°C with the current building. However, implementing the studied combinations of refurbishment measures diminished future overheating. Combinations incorporating active measures demonstrated minimal change compared to the current achievable indoor environment, though consuming significantly more energy.

1 Introduction

Extreme heat poses a significant risk to human health. Indoors at workplaces, adverse thermal conditions can lead to errors, reduced performance, and even accidents (Lan et al. 2011, Ioannou et al. 2023). In healthcare facilities, with patients who may be vulnerable and therefore rely on staff to be vigilant and careful, heat can have particularly serious consequences.

Rising temperatures and recurring heat waves increase demand for cooling, especially in warmer climate zones. Currently, energy used for space cooling globally accounts for 20% of the CO₂ emissions from buildings. With increasing temperatures caused by climate change, the energy used to cool buildings is projected to triple by 2050 (IEA 2018).

Being indoors in buildings can protect people from severe climate exposures, but the construction industry currently accounts for 36% of all energy-related emissions. While these percentages might be lower in an African context, it is crucial to emphasise sustainable practices in the building sector now rather than delaying it (United Nations 2021). This includes more widespread use of designs and technologies that can moderate indoor environments at low energy use, preferably by passive means, by utilising renewable energy, and by using sustainable materials.

This deliverable reports on measurements of thermal exposures in the maternity wards of four healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe, South Africa, and Sweden. Also, the study evaluates through numerical simulations the effect on the indoor thermal conditions and energy use of selected building-related mitigation interventions in a maternity ward at the Mt. Darwin Hospital in Zimbabwe under different climate scenarios.

1.1 Objectives

This study aims to quantify and evaluate thermal exposures in selected healthcare facilities through monitoring of indoor thermal environment parameters, and through numerical simulations to assess the effects on heat exposure, sustainability, and cost of selected building design measures and projected climate change.

This component of the HIGH Horizons study is linked to the health workers impact baseline assessment (deliverable 2.10) and together these reports inform the co-design and selection of health facility adaptation interventions (deliverable 3.6).

1.2 Background

1.2.1 Indices for evaluation of thermal exposures

A person's thermal sensation is mainly related to the thermal balance of the body (Havenith 2005). Thermal balance exists when the body's internal heat production equals the heat loss to the environment. Indoors, humans exchange heat with the surroundings mainly through convection and radiation. Convective heat transfer depends on the air temperature and speed, while radiant heat loss depends mainly on the temperature of the surfaces in a room when the direct solar load is negligible. In warm or hot environments or at high activity levels, evaporation of sweat becomes increasingly crucial for the exchange of thermal energy between the body and its surroundings. The evaporation potential depends on the air humidity and the clothing moisture permeability. Therefore, the indoor thermal environment should be characterised by monitoring, including the air temperature, mean radiant temperature, air humidity, and air speed. The mean radiant temperature is often approximated by measurement of globe temperature (described below), while instrumentation to measure air speed is costly and typically requires continuous supervision. Airspeed was therefore not

measured as part of the evaluation of the health worker heat exposure in this task but only approximated through assumptions.

Several standardised indices exist to evaluate thermal exposure, both in comfortable and stressful environments. However, the indices were developed with standard populations (mostly university students in their twenties who were readily available to participate in the underlying experiments). Therefore, the index limits may require adjustment if they are to be used with more susceptible populations, e.g., pregnant women or newborns.

1.2.1.1 Operative temperature

The operative temperature integrates the air and mean radiant temperatures in a straightforward index often used to assess thermal comfort in buildings based on different indoor environment quality categories. Table 1 shows the quality categories, their explanations, and the upper temperature limit for the cooling season in buildings with mechanical cooling (EN-ISO 16798-1 2019).

Table 1. Explanation of indoor environment quality classes and maximum temperature limits for the cooling season in buildings with mechanical cooling (EN-ISO 16798-1 2019)

Quality category	Level of expectation	Explanation	Maximum operative temperature at seated / standing activity (°C)
Class I	High	Occupants with special needs (children, elderly, handicapped)	25 ¹⁾ / 24 ²⁾
Class II	Medium	Normal level used for design and operation	26 ¹⁾ / 25 ²⁾
Class III	Moderate	Acceptable environment. Some risk of reduced performance	27 ¹⁾ / 26 ²⁾
Class IV	Low	Should only be used for a short time of the year in spaces with short occupancy	- ³⁾ / 28 ²⁾

Note: 1) Assumes seated, resting activity at 1.2 met
 2) Assumes standing, light activity at 1.6 met
 3) No class IV maximum temperature limit at seated activity.

In buildings without mechanical cooling, occupants may adapt to higher temperatures and more considerable temperature variation than in climate-controlled environments (Brager & de Dear 1998). For such buildings, an adaptive thermal comfort model has been suggested that determines the neutral (comfort) indoor temperature based on the monthly average outdoor temperature. The adaptive model applies to non-industrial buildings used for occupancy with near-sedentary activities, where there is easy access to operable windows and where occupants can freely adapt their clothing (EN-ISO 16798-I 2019). Figure 1 shows the optimal temperature and the quality class limits for maximum temperatures at different outdoor running mean temperatures.

Figure 1. Optimal temperature and quality class limits for maximum temperatures as determined with the adaptive model of thermal comfort (EN-ISO 16798-I 2019)

Note: Class IV in parenthesis as the adaptive model is defined for only three quality categories.

For example, for Zimbabwe Table 4 (see 2.1.2) indicates an average outdoor temperature of 29.8°C for October resulting in a recommended maximum indoor temperature of 31.6°C in a building without mechanical cooling, while Table 1 recommends a maximum of 26°C if the temperature in the building was controlled with a cooling system. Therefore, applying the adaptive model will yield large

energy savings. In Stockholm with a much colder climate, the difference between the models presented in Table 1 and Table 4 is almost negligible, as no adaptation to high temperature is likely to occur.

1.2.1.2 Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)

The PMV index predicts the mean value of the thermal sensation of a large group of persons as a function of their physical activity (metabolic rate), clothing insulation and the four environmental parameters air temperature, mean radiant temperature, air speed and air humidity (Fanger 1970, ISO 7730-2006). The PMV index is based on the heat balance of the body, and index values range from -3 (cold) over 0 (neutral) to +3 (hot). The PMV index is typically used to evaluate and design moderate thermal environments. Table 2 shows the quality classes and their corresponding PMV limits (EN-ISO 16798-1 2019).

Table 2. Quality classes and corresponding PMV limits for mechanically cooled (and heated) buildings (EN-ISO 16798-1 2019)

Quality category	Thermal state of the body as a whole
I	-0.2 < PMV < +0.2
II	-0.5 < PMV < +0.5
III	-0.7 < PMV < +0.7
IV	-1 < PMV < +1

1.2.1.3 Wet-Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT)

The WBGT provides a screening method to evaluate the heat stress to which a person is exposed (ISO 7243-2017).

Without direct solar load, as is often the case indoors, WBGT may be calculated from

$$WBGT = 0.7 \cdot t_{nw} + 0.3 \cdot t_g$$

t_{nw} is the natural wet bulb temperature that can be estimated with equations provided in EN-ISO 7243 (2017) (more precisely, equations D.1 and D.2). t_g is the globe temperature (described below).

Evaluation of the WBGT requires knowledge of the exerted physical activity and the insulation and vapour permeability of the clothing. In this deliverable, the calculation of WBGT assumed resting to moderate physical activity, clothing insulation around 0.6 clo, and moisture permeability of 0.38 (reference values). Table 3 provides reference values for the WBGT for these values of activity and clothing.

Table 3. Reference values for WBGT for acclimatized and unacclimatized people for three metabolic rates and for standard clothing with $I_{cl} = 0.6$ clo and $i_m = 0.38$ (ISO 7243-2017)

Physical activity	Met rate (W)	WBGT limit for persons acclimatized to heat (°C)	WBGT limit for persons unacclimatized to heat (°C)
Resting metabolic rate	115	33	32
Low metabolic rate	180	30	29
Moderate metabolic rate	300	28	26

1.2.2 Building interventions

One of the main functions of a building is to protect its occupants from the outdoors. In a poorly designed building, the indoors can become hotter than outdoors or excessive use of energy may be required to condition the indoor environment to comfortable temperatures. Building design is influenced by various factors, including geographical location, construction conventions and traditions, often rooted in available local resources used for construction. Geographical location determines the local climate, which influences the thermal indoor climate, the energy used for climatisation and the selection of appropriate measures to keep buildings comfortable.

The need to focus on resilient and adaptable buildings will increase in the coming years due to an expected climate-induced temperature increase. The resultant effects on thermal comfort can be evaluated with numerical simulations of buildings, considering projected changes in the climate at the site of the building. Such simulations also enable evaluation of the effect of building-related mitigation measures or changes in occupant behaviour.

1.2.2.1 Passive climatisation of buildings

Passive climatisation of buildings includes measures that do not require the supply of electrical, cooling, or heating energy. A passive measure could include the geometry of the building or the use of specific construction materials, affecting both heat gains and heat transfer. Passive building design may be used to increase sustainability before implementing active solutions that use energy.

1.2.2.2 Natural ventilation

Many modern and airtight buildings use mechanical ventilation systems with electricity-powered fans to dilute and remove polluted indoor air or control indoor temperature with an air conditioning system. More than 50% of a commercial building's energy consumption can be allocated to an air conditioning system in the tropics. Thus, natural ventilation can be a sustainable alternative if feasible in the given climate (Wong et al. 2020). Natural ventilation can be obtained by naturally generated airflow through the building, often created by openings such as ventilation slots, windows, or doors. The efficiency of natural ventilation depends on the geometry of the building, the indoor-outdoor temperature difference, and the prevailing wind.

1.2.2.3 Cool roofs

When solar irradiation reaches the roof of a building, the solar reflectivity of the roof material influences the roof surface temperature and can reduce the transfer of solar heat to the interior. A white material would usually be reflective, but materials with darker colours can also be effective if the colour pigments are reflective in the near-infrared portion of the solar spectrum.

1.2.2.4 Accumulation of heat in constructions

Materials that can store large amounts of heat at modest temperature change are labelled materials with high thermal mass. Materials with high thermal mass, e.g. concrete, can be incorporated into the building to lower temperature fluctuations.

In climates with considerable diurnal temperature variation, including thermally heavy materials at appropriate locations in the construction can result in good thermal conditioning of the building at low energy use. This means that buildings can regulate indoor temperatures by smoothing out temperature fluctuations and reducing the need for active heating or cooling systems.

1.2.2.5 Active climatisation of buildings

Active climatisation of buildings provides robust temperature moderation, which passive design solutions cannot gain. Some buildings might even need an active heating and cooling system, especially with high interior heating loads. Depending on its configuration, an active system can also moderate the air quality by supplying outdoor air to a building or dehumidifying the indoor air. Active measures are often more costly than passive measures, and they use energy for their operation. In hospitals or healthcare facilities, contaminated air may pose a risk to patients and staff. Supplying clean outdoor air or filtered air may reduce the risk of infection.

The heat exposure, energy use and sustainability of selected passive and active building interventions were quantified based on numerical simulations of a selected case building, Mt Darwin District Hospital in Zimbabwe.

2 Methodology

2.1 Measurement of thermal exposures in healthcare facilities

2.1.1 Measurement sites

2.1.1.1 South Africa

In South Africa, measurements so far have been made in two facilities situated in the Tshwane district, Gauteng Province.

Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre (CHC) includes an emergency unit, maternal obstetrics and child services, and curative services. Other services offered include primary health and rehabilitation services. In addition, the facility offers peer counselling, a crisis centre for gender-based violence and sexual assault victims, antiretroviral therapy (ART) adherence clubs, COVID screening, and home delivery of medication.

Mamelodi District Hospital is situated 3,5 km from Stanza Bopape CHC. It is a referral centre for patients requiring a higher level of care, including pregnant women with obstetric emergencies from Stanza Bopape CHC and other surrounding feeder clinics. The hospital offers the following services: Clinical specialities in fields of Medicine, Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Paediatrics, Psychiatry, Radiology, Emergency Medical Services, Trauma, and NCDs clinical management of HIV/AIDS, and TB, screening and laboratory, HIV testing and TB.

2.1.1.2 Zimbabwe

In Zimbabwe, three public healthcare facilities within Mashonaland Central Province were enrolled for the study. The three facilities are Mt Darwin District Hospital, Dotito and Chitse Rural Healthcare Centres. Indoor and outdoor environmental measurements were carried out at all the sites but had varied start dates for measurements.

Mt Darwin District Hospital is situated 160 kilometres from Zimbabwe's capital city, Harare, and is a referral hospital in the district for patients requiring an advanced level of care. The hospital offers services for its 240,728 estimated population in the district (Zimstat 2022). These services include curative, preventative, maternity, postnatal, inpatient, outpatient, male, female and children wards, theatre, laboratory, and pharmacy.

Dotito Rural Healthcare Centre is the oldest facility in the district. It is a primary care clinic 28 kilometres from Mt Darwin District Hospital. The clinic is managed by a nurse in charge who oversees all departments. Services offered include

curative (chronic condition screening, treatment, monitoring and follow-up, TB screening, initiation, and management), maternity-related services (antenatal care, booking follow-up visits, delivery) and postnatal care.

Chitse Rural Healthcare Centre is situated 18 km from Mt Darwin Hospital and is a primary healthcare facility in the district. The clinic offers the same services as Dotito and is managed by a nurse. Services offered include curative, maternity-related services, postnatal care, outpatient and inpatient-related services.

2.1.1.3 Sweden

The Swedish site is Karolinska Sjukhuset in the northern part of Stockholm. The hospital started receiving patients in 2016 and was completed in 2018. Karolinska is a national referral centre for high-risk pregnancies and deliveries and a District referral centre for specialised high-risk pregnancies and deliveries. Karolinska Sjukhuset has 3700 births per year, the majority being high-risk pregnancies.

2.1.2 Climate data

Table 4 shows aggregated climate data for the measurement sites.

Table 4. Monthly average high temperature, daily mean temperature, and average relative humidity at the three measurement sites in South Africa, Zimbabwe, and Sweden

Location	Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Year
Zimbabwe Mt Darwin	Ave. high (°C)	28.2	27.9	28.2	27.7	27.2	25.4	25.8	29.7	33.4	34.7	32.9	29.7	29.2
	Daily mean (°C)	24.7	24.2	24.2	23.2	21.9	19.9	20.2	23.9	27.8	29.8	28.6	26.2	24.5
	Ave. RH (%)	83	86	83	76	65	61	55	43	34	37	52	72	62
South Africa Pretoria	Ave. high (°C)	29.1	28.8	27.6	24.1	22.6	19.1	19.1	22.6	27.1	28.4	28.5	28.6	25.5
	Daily mean (°C)	25.2	24.8	23.5	20.3	18.4	14.7	14.8	18.4	22.8	24.5	24.9	25.1	21.4
	Ave. RH (%)	65	65	64	60	49	48	45	37	34	42	51	61	52
Sweden Stockholm	Ave. high (°C)	-0.6	0.2	3.3	9	14	18	21	20	16	9.9	5.1	1.6	9.9
	Daily mean (°C)	-1.7	-1.0	1.6	6.9	12	16	19	18	14	8.2	4.1	0.6	8.2
	Ave. RH (%)	87	86	81	72	71	72	74	75	79	81	86	87	79

Under the Köppen-Geiger climate classification Mount Darwin and Pretoria feature a humid subtropical climate (Cwa), while Stockholm has a continental climate (Dfb).

2.1.3 Measurements and instruments

2.1.3.1 Air temperature, globe temperature, and air humidity

In the following, the instruments used and the parameters that were measured in the healthcare facilities are briefly described. It is assumed that the buildings are in use at all times of the day and year, and therefore, no specific occupied periods used to assess the thermal conditions were defined.

Air temperature: The air temperature determines the heat transfer to or from the body by convection. The air temperature is a key parameter for several indices that evaluate heat exposure.

Globe temperature: The globe temperature expresses an integrated measure of the radiant and air temperatures, and it depends on the energy balance between the globe's convective and radiant heat exchanges. The mean radiant temperature can be used to evaluate radiant heat fluxes and, thus, the amount of radiant heat exchanged between a person and an enclosure. Indoors, surface temperatures may deviate considerably, particularly with intense and prolonged solar irradiation on and in the building envelope. The globe temperature approximates the operative temperature, which combines the air- and mean radiant temperature by weighing with the convective and radiant heat transfer coefficients. Therefore, with a known air temperature (and airspeed), the globe temperature can be used to estimate the mean radiant temperature.

Air humidity: The air humidity influences the evaporative heat loss from a person. Under comfortable conditions, typically at temperatures below 26°C and at sedentary activity, air humidity has only a modest influence on heat loss. Still, it is considerable with higher temperatures or activity levels when evaporation of sweat is required to sustain the body's heat balance. Air humidity is a crucial parameter when assessing heat exposure. In contrast to temperature, recommendations on air humidities are not generally agreed upon, but a typical recommended range indoors is between 20% and 60% RH.

2.1.3.2 Instruments

The thermal measurements were taken with two types of data loggers (Onset Hobo MX1101 and U12-012). All devices measured air temperature and air humidity, but some devices were also equipped with external sensors for measuring globe- and air temperatures. A polished metal cylinder covering the pt-100 sensor element shields the external air temperature sensor from radiation. The cylinder allows the air to move around the sensor element. A simplified globe temperature sensor consists of a globe (ping-pong ball) in the centre of which another pt-100 temperature sensor measures the globe temperature. The array of devices was mounted on a small wooden plate for easy installation on a suitable wall or other appropriate location. Figure 2 shows a measurement device with external sensors for the measurement of globe- and air temperatures located in a doctor dispatch room at Karolinska Sjukhuset in Sweden.

Figure 2. Measurement device at Karolinska Sjukhuset

Before deploying the loggers with external sensors for measuring air- and globe temperatures, the devices were calibrated in a temperature-controlled environment at the Technical University of Denmark. The devices were then transported to the relevant consortium partners participating in the annual consortium meeting held in Stockholm on 9-10 October 2023 to be brought back and installed in the African facilities. At Karolinska Sjukhuset, the devices were installed in connection with the consortium meeting.

With the available instrumentation, measurements could only be carried out in some rooms in the facilities. Measurement locations were selected to represent rooms where the staff had the longest or highest exposure. Placing the devices was not straightforward, considering the room's interior and activities. Upon scrutiny, the devices were placed in areas of the room where they seemed unlikely to interfere.

Due to practicalities with the transportation and setup of the measurement devices and the time-consuming ethical approval required to access the health facilities in some countries, measurements commenced at different starting dates. Download and data processing for this deliverable occurred in late December 2023 or January 2024. So far, measurements in Sweden covered autumn and winter seasons; in Zimbabwe, late spring/summer; and in South Africa, the summer. Measurements will continue for up to a year in each facility to cover all seasons. Table 5 shows the number of rooms and the period covered in each facility.

Table 5. Overview of facilities, rooms and preliminary measurements periods covered by this deliverable

Country	Facility	Room	Start date	Date for download of data
Zimbabwe	Mt Darwin	Consultation Postnatal	06 Nov 2023	07 Dec 2023
		Delivery	19 Sep 2023	07 Dec 2023
		Neonatal	06 Nov 2023	07 Dec 2023
		Postnatal patient room	03 Nov 2023	07 Dec 2023
		Theatre	06 Nov 2023	08 Dec 2023
		Outdoor	28 Sep 2023	07 Dec 2024
South Africa	Mamelodi	Antenatal	11 Dec 2023	08 Jan 2024
		Neonatal	11 Dec 2023	08 Jan 2024
		Postnatal ward	11 Dec 2023	08 Jan 2024
	Stanza	Admission	11 Dec 2023	08 Jan 2024
Sweden	Karolinska	Rest	11 Oct 2023	15 Jan 2024
		Midwife dispatch	11 Oct 2023	15 Jan 2024
		Doctor dispatch	11 Oct 2023	15 Jan 2024
		Patient room	11 Oct 2023	15 Jan 2024

2.1.4 Data processing

Data retrieved from the devices with external sensors was first adjusted according to their calibration algorithms, and quality was checked before further analysis by inspecting aggregated values (mean, min, max) and the general progress of the recorded data.

Thermal comfort and heat stress indices were then calculated and added to the dataset. The index calculation required assumptions regarding activity level and clothing properties. In rooms with mostly standing, light work, an activity level of 1.5 met was assumed and with seated work or resting it was assumed to be 1.2 met. For calculation of the WBGT index, one-hour running mean values were used. Table 6 lists the values that were used at the sites and rooms where measurements were made. A standard clothing insulation value of $I_{cl} = 0.6$ clo and moisture permeability of $i_m = 0.38$ was used in the African facilities. In Sweden, an $I_{cl} = 0.7$ clo was used to evaluate the PMV index. This corresponded to underwear, socks, shoes, trousers, a short-sleeve T-shirt and a thin cardigan.

Table 6. Values for physical activity and clothing insulation used in the calculation of thermal comfort and heat stress indices

Country	Site	Room	M (met)	I_{cl} (clo)
Zimbabwe	All	All	1.5	0.6
South Africa	Mamelodi	Admission	1.2	0.6
	Mamelodi, Stanza	All but admission	1.5	0.6
Sweden	Karolinska Sjukhuset	Postnatal patient room	1.5	0.7
		All other	1.2	

Outdoor weather data for Stockholm was downloaded from Observatoriekullen a few kilometres from Karolinska Sjukhuset (SMHI 2024). Hourly values were available for relative air humidity and global radiation, but only recordings made at 6:00 hrs and 18:00 hrs were available for air temperature. Hourly values for outdoor air temperature were therefore based on linear interpolation between the recordings. At Mt Darwin District Hospital in Zimbabwe, a logger placed

outdoors recorded outdoor temperature, relative air humidity, solar radiation, and windspeed in five-minute intervals. South Africa needed more readily available access to meteorological data.

2.2 Simulation of thermal exposures and environmental impact of building refurbishment

This section of the deliverable reports on evaluations by numerical simulation of the indoor environment, cost and environmental impact of passive and active building refurbishment actions targeted at a healthcare facility in Zimbabwe. The resilience of the building and refurbishment actions to mitigate the effects of climate change were evaluated with the current and projected future climates. The simulations are described in detail in the supplement.

2.2.1 Model setup

A virtual model of the maternity ward at Mt Darwin District Hospital was created based on observations in the hospital case building. The model was used for a year-long simulation of the indoor environment and energy use with a weather file representing the location of the hospital with the current climate and with a projection to 2080 based on the IPCC Third Assessment Report. Properties on the building were collected through checklists completed by CeSHHAR. Data included the layout of specific rooms, e.g. area, window properties and equipment. Also, information was collected on user behaviour, describing the number of people and the typical use pattern of a room.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the virtual model and the technical properties used to simulate the building. The simulation software IDA ICE (v4.99 SP23) was used for indoor environment and energy simulations, SimaPro (v9.4.0.2) was used for the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analyses, and production processes were based on the Ecoinvent v3 database.

Figure 3. Virtual model of the building and the simulated patient room

Figure 4. Materials currently used in the facility and their physical properties

Note: U-values in W/(m² K), SRI: Solar reflection Index (-), G: Window radiation transmission property (-)

2.2.2 Refurbishment scenarios

The following refurbishment scenarios were compared:

- *Baseline model*: Initial model to predict the indoor environment in the existing building without implementing any refurbishment scenarios
- *Combination 1*: The baseline model with added reflective roof paint and ventilation grills in the exterior walls
- *Combination 2*: The baseline model with added reflective roof paint, ventilation grills in the exterior walls, as well as insulated ceiling and exterior walls

- *Combination 3*: The baseline model with added reflective roof paint, insulated ceiling and exterior walls, new windows, a large overhang and split air conditioning units.
- *Combination 4*: The baseline model with added reflective roof paint, insulated ceiling and exterior walls, a large overhang and an air handling unit with cooling

Figure 5 shows the individual refurbishment actions used to improve the climate resiliency of the building.

Figure 5. Refurbishment actions used to improve the resiliency of the building

2.2.3 Climate scenarios

Current weather was represented by a dataset from Mt Darwin with data from 2007-2021. A future weather file was generated using the methodologies presented by Jentsch et al. (2013) based on the Third Assessment Report model summary data of the A2 scenario by the IPCC. The A2 scenario represents a heterogeneous world with high emissions (IPCC 2000). Thus, a new weather file was generated for the year 2080 based on the existing weather data from a specific location.

2.2.4 Evaluation of the simulation outcome

The indoor environment in the hospital was evaluated based on the number of hours when the indoor operative temperature exceeded 32°C (WHO 2018). A CO₂ concentration of 1000 ppm or higher signalled unsatisfactory air quality. The global warming potential of the measures and their life cycle cost were also evaluated based on local prices found online from either Zimbabwe or South Africa. The assessment period for these calculations was 50 years, aligned with commonly used practices for LCA and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) calculations of buildings. In the case of active solutions, their energy consumption was integrated into the analysis.

3 Results

3.1 Measurement of thermal exposures in healthcare facilities

3.1.1 Indoor temperature

For one selected room and facility in each of the three countries, Figure 6 shows that the temperature and its diurnal variation was considerably higher in Zimbabwe than in South Africa and Sweden. At the Swedish site, the tight indoor climate control in the newly constructed building resulted in a stable temperature that was generally within the comfortable range. Measurements made in the other rooms in the three countries indicated the same trends as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Example of temperature profiles as measured in selected rooms in the health facilities in Sweden, Zimbabwe, and South Africa

Figure 7 shows the temperature quality class distribution for all facilities for all rooms and measurement periods. For Zimbabwe and South Africa, the temperature limits for summer were used, while for Sweden, the temperature limits for winter were used. In Sweden, the recorded temperatures mainly were within quality category I or II and only in the Doctor Dispatch, the temperature had some excursions to higher values close to the class III/IV temperature limit. In Zimbabwe and South Africa, temperatures were well above the recommended limits for comfortable indoor conditions. They may be better evaluated with dedicated heat stress indices or the adaptive comfort model.

Figure 7. Operative temperature quality category distribution across countries, facilities, and rooms

For Sweden, Table 7 shows that the predicted mean vote (average of recordings during the whole measurement period) generally was between neutral and slightly

cool. Only in the Doctor dispatch where high temperatures were recorded and in the Patient room with an activity level higher than resting, mean votes on the warmer side of neutral were predicted. With the temperatures measured in Sweden until now, assessment of thermal comfort according to adaptive comfort theory is not meaningful as 80% of the measured outdoor temperatures were lower than 10°C, which is the temperature limit for using the model. In Zimbabwe and South Africa, heat exposure will be assessed with the WBGT (heat stress).

Table 7. Overall thermal sensation as predicted with the PMV index for Karolinska Sjukhuset in Sweden

Room	Average PMV	Minimum PMV	Maximum PMV
Patient Room	-0.1	-0.4	0.5
Doctor dispatch	-0.2	-0.8	0.8
Midwife dispatch	-0.4	-1,2	0.1
Rest	-0.3	-0.7	0

3.1.2 Air humidity

Indoors, the relative air humidity depends on the outdoor and indoor temperatures, the air exchange rate (amount of ventilation), and the indoor sources of moisture. At low temperatures, air cannot contain much moisture before saturation is reached. Therefore, when cool outdoor air is heated and supplied to a warmer building, the relative air humidity may be low. This is supported by Figure 8, which shows that in Sweden, the relative air humidity was lower than 20% RH in 25% of the recordings and lower than 40% RH in around 90% of the recordings. This may affect the staff's perception of dry air and cause symptoms such as dry mucous membranes in the eyes, nose, and mouth, and dry skin (Wolkoff 2018). In contrast, in South Africa and Zimbabwe the relative air humidity was higher than 40% RH in around 75% of the recordings (except in the Delivery and Postnatal bedroom, which experienced periods with very high air temperatures and therefore lower relative air humidities). In combination with a high operative temperature, the air humidity may reduce evaporation of sweat, which is required to sustain the body's heat balance. Also, sustained periods with

high air humidity may cause mould growth on organic interior surfaces (e.g. wooden materials, wallpaper).

Figure 8. Cumulative distributions of the relative air humidity in the healthcare facilities

3.1.3 Assessment of the heat exposure of healthcare workers in Zimbabwe and South Africa

The heat exposure of the healthcare workers in Zimbabwe and South Africa was evaluated with the WBGT index, considering the combined influence of both temperature and air humidity on the body's heat transfer. Figure 9 shows the distribution of the WBGT index in Mt Darwin Hospital in Zimbabwe and separately for the two different facilities in South Africa, Mamelodi and Stanza Bopape. In South Africa, the WBGT was below the reference limit for unacclimatised persons performing work at low or moderate metabolic rates almost all the time, while in Zimbabwe, the reference limit for moderate work was exceeded in around 7% of the measurements. Reference limits reflect unacclimatised persons, as healthcare workers may or may not be acclimatised to heat, e.g. they are considered unacclimatised if they have been exposed to moderate temperatures for just some days.

Even though air temperatures reached relatively high levels, the air humidity during these periods was moderate, preventing excessively high WBGTs. Also, the difference between the measured air- and globe temperatures was low (mean: 0.25°C, range: -5.4°C to 8.1°C) indicating that long-wave radiant exposure caused by thermal radiation from hot interior surfaces was modest.

Figure 9. Histograms showing the distribution of the WBGT in Mt Darwin Hospital in Zimbabwe and in the Mamelodi and Stanza facilities in South Africa

Note: The solid green line indicates the reference limit for unacclimatized persons at moderate physical activity and the dashed red line for unacclimatized persons at low metabolic rate.

3.1.4 Relation between indoor and outdoor temperature and temperature transients

Indoor occupancy may moderate the exposure to heat as compared with outdoors. Direct solar irradiation can be eliminated, and peak temperatures may be reduced by heat accumulation in the construction. For two rooms at Mt Darwin District Hospital, Figure 10 shows simultaneous measurements of the indoor operative temperature and the outdoor temperature. The moderating effect on the heat exposure of indoors is evident in the Neonatal room but less pronounced in the Delivery room. However, the peak temperatures differed somewhat from the outdoor temperature peaks in all rooms. The rooms at Mt. Darwin District Hospital were largely grouped into two categories. Neonatal and Theatre experienced only modest diurnal temperature swings, while in the Delivery, Postnatal consultation, and Postnatal ward, the temperature variation was considerably larger. The building has good heat accumulation properties as the exterior walls consist of a double brick layer covered with cement plaster, and the floor is made of concrete covered with tiles. The roof is made from an asbestos plate. As the rooms are in the same building, the different temperature amplitudes can be caused by the orientation of the windows or shading from neighbouring buildings or vegetation.

Figure 10 indicates that the outdoor temperature decreased during the night, enabling outdoor air to cool down the building structure and reduce the risk of overheating during the day. For Mt Darwin District Hospital, Figure 11 confirms that the heat exposure in all studied rooms was clearly higher in the afternoon than in the morning.

Figure 10. Association between outdoor and indoor temperature at Mt Darwin District Hospital

Figure 11. Comparison of operative temperature measured in the morning (10 am to 12 pm) and in the afternoon (2 pm to 4 pm) at Mt Darwin District Hospital, Zimbabwe

3.2 Simulation of thermal exposures and environmental impact of building refurbishment

3.2.1 Indoor environment

With the assumed setup of the use pattern and the properties of the current building, the indoor temperature and air quality exceeded 32°C and 1000 ppm during the 2 380 and 1 860 hours out of the 8 760 hours in a year, respectively. Figure 12 shows the outdoor and simulated indoor temperature for a week in November before any refurbishment.

Reflective roof paint increased the solar reflection index of the roof from -6 to 109, and was the most cost-effective way to reduce overheating. Consequently, the combination of reflective roof paint and ventilation grills in the exterior walls resulted in only 1 hour above 32°C. It also had the lowest carbon footprint and life-cycle costing of all the evaluated refurbishment combinations.

Figure 12. Room and attic temperatures with and without refurbishment with reflective roof paint and ventilation grills in the external walls

The active systems generally provided comfortable indoor conditions, but the associated costs and environmental impacts were considerably higher than with the passive systems. Sustainable operation of the active systems will, therefore, require the installation of photovoltaics.

3.2.2 LCC and LCA

Table 8 shows the outcome of the analysis of the LCC and LCA of each refurbishment measure, for LCA expressed as the Global Warming Potential (GWP) of a measure. Both the LCC and LCA calculations were carried out by ISO 14040 (2006). Thus, the LCA and LCC included both materials and energy consumption for each measure. The LCA only focused on the measures added to the building and did not include current existing components or the current energy use. When each component reaches its end of life, it must be replaced. For energy consumption, an energy mix for Zimbabwe was chosen, whereas the majority of the remaining processes were 'global,' thus not necessarily very accurate for the location. Each process had a predefined amount of transport included.

Table 8. LCC and GWP for the individual refurbishment measures

Refurbishment measure	LCC (EUR/m²)	GWP (kg-CO₂-eq/m²/yr)
Reflective roof paint	4.72	0.046
Insulation of ceiling towards attic	5.48	0.092
Insulation of exterior walls	45.87	0.209
Overhang above windows	16.23	0.309
Air grilles in facades	0.10	$6.12 \cdot 10^{-5}$
New windows	25.63	0.290
Installation of ventilation system	537.28	34.55
Installation of air conditioning system	626.58	51.81

The active measures were far less cost-effective as there was no energy consumption from the passive measures.

Due to the high energy consumption associated with the combinations involving active measures, there were significant financial and environmental drawbacks. For the Maternity Ward, it would be possible to fit a photovoltaic system on the roof. Based on the electricity consumption of the AHU and the roof orientation, the most optimal placement for the photovoltaic system was towards the north. This position allowed for the maximum generation of usable electricity, ensuring

efficient utilisation of the system’s capacity. The roof slope is 19 degrees, and for a standard 400 Wp panel, that would generate about 658 kWh/year, with an estimated system loss of 14%.

Figure 13 compares construction cost, LLC and LCA for a combination of refurbishment measures that includes a central air handling unit with cooling, reflective roof paint and 100 mm insulation in the ceiling towards the attic and in the exterior walls, and a large overhang to provide shading for the windows to reduce operation time of the ventilation system.

Figure 13. Construction cost, LCC and LCA for a combination of refurbishment measures (labelled combination 4) with and without a 6.4 kWp photovoltaic system including a battery

3.2.3 Effect of projected climate scenarios

Without any refurbishment action, the projection for the year 2080 resulted in a 15 percentage-point increase in the number of hours with an indoor temperature higher than 32°C. However, implementing any of the refurbishment combinations diminished future overheating. With the active measures, indoor heat exposures changed only insignificantly from now and towards 2080, but the environmental impact and the cost were significantly higher.

Figure 14 shows the number of hours with an indoor temperature higher than 32°C, now and in 2080. Without implementation of any refurbishment, the periods

with high indoor temperature will increase considerably, while even the passive measures in combination 1 and 2 were able to reduce the duration of periods with excessively high temperatures.

Figure 14. Number of hours with an indoor temperature higher than 32°C, now and in 2080 without any refurbishment made to the building and with refurbishment combinations 1 and 2

4 Discussion

4.1 Measurement of thermal exposures in healthcare facilities

The earliest measurements in the healthcare facilities commenced in Zimbabwe in late September 2023 and the latest in South Africa in early December 2023. So far, measurements in Sweden cover only the colder seasons (since October 2023). The build-up of data sets to evaluate thermal exposures will continue in the coming period to enable more thorough evaluation during all seasons.

In parallel with the measurements, time-motion studies involving the healthcare workers in the three countries have been or will soon be carried out. These studies involve measurement of physiological and subjective parameters that, combined

with information on the indoor environment in the facilities, can be used to analyse both thermal exposures and their consequences for the healthcare workers (see deliverable 2.10).

The snapshot of the thermal conditions in the healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe and South Africa presented in this deliverable shows that temperatures during periods were high, in particular in the afternoons. During these periods, healthcare workers should be particularly aware of using adaptation or mitigation measures to heat. When the indoor temperature was high, the relative air humidity was generally modest, which resulted in the WBGT being lower than the reference values in most of the measurements. The globe- and air temperatures were rather similar indicating that the interior surfaces in the studied rooms did not reach excessively high temperature due to solar irradiation during the day. The measurements in Sweden represented autumn and winter, and the staff at Karolinska Sjukhuset generally experienced temperatures in or near the comfort range, although they expressed regularly feeling cool. Very low air humidities could contribute to a feeling of dryness in the eyes, nose, mouth, or skin.

4.2 Simulation of thermal exposures and environmental impact of building refurbishment

Various measures to mitigate excessive overheating were explored through numerical simulations. Generally, the solutions were included due to their potential to reduce overheating. The simulation outcome indicated trade-offs and interdependencies between the different solutions that complicated the identification of the most effective and balanced solutions. The findings, therefore, highlighted the complexity of addressing multiple performance factors in healthcare facilities and the need for integrated approaches to optimise the indoor environment.

When using the future climate data, an increase in overheating was found, which was greater for the baseline model than for the combinations of refurbishment measures. This suggests that avoiding the implementation of refurbishment measures will increase the future risk of overheating. The increased cooling demand to avoid overheating aligns well with the projection of increased global energy consumption for cooling. Consequently, passive refurbishment measures could be an attractive way to avoid increased carbon emissions and to address issues with overheating and high energy consumption in the future.

5 Conclusion

Indoor temperatures in the healthcare facilities in Zimbabwe and South Africa were high during periods, in particular in the afternoons. During these periods, healthcare workers should be particularly aware of using adaptation or mitigation measures to heat. However, when the indoor temperature was high, the relative air humidity was generally modest, which resulted in the WBGT being lower than the reference values in most of the measurements. The globe- and air temperatures were rather similar indicating that the interior surfaces in the studied rooms did not reach excessively high temperature. The measurements in Sweden represented autumn and winter, and the staff at Karolinska Sjukhuset generally experienced temperatures in or near the comfort range.

Numerical simulations of Mt Darwin District hospital showed that it was possible to almost eliminate time with temperatures above the health-risk limit with combinations of the refurbishment solutions. As the associated costs and environmental impacts were considerably greater with the active than with the passive solutions, the implementation of photovoltaics should be considered with active solutions.

The projection for the year 2080 showed a 15-percentage point increase in yearly hours with indoor temperatures higher than 32°C with the current building. However, by implementing the studied combinations of refurbishment measures, future overheating was diminished. Combinations incorporating active measures demonstrated minimal change compared to the current achievable indoor environment, though consuming a significantly higher amount of energy.

6 Future work

To cover all seasons, the measurements presented in this deliverable will continue for a duration of up to a year in each country. When they are completed, aggregated measures of the thermal exposures will be combined with observations from the time-motion study and used to generate associations between the responses of the healthcare personnel and their thermal exposures. The associations will be used in a risk assessment tool that will be reported in deliverable 2.9 due in December 2025.

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